

Numerical algorithm to reproduce Partial Rank Correlation Coefficients (PRCC) diagrams

Description:

Pseudocode to reproduce figures 6, 7, 8, 9 of manuscript number **EPJS-D-25-00637R3**.

- Figures 6 and 7 are represented as bar plot.
- Figure 8 is represented as scatter plot.

The parameter set used here is mentioned in the manuscript.

The global sensitivity analysis is implemented through three modular pseudocodes. First, model parameters are sampled within predefined bounds using Latin Hypercube Sampling (Pseudocode 2). Second, the mathematical model is numerically solved for each sampled parameter set to obtain terminal state variables (Pseudocode 3). Finally, Partial Rank Correlation Coefficients (PRCCs) are computed to quantify the influence of individual parameters on model outputs while controlling for the effects of other parameters (Pseudocode 4). This modular structure ensures transparency, reproducibility, and ease of implementation.

Pseudocode 4 PRCC-based global sensitivity analysis using Latin Hypercube Sampling

- 1: **Input:** Sample size N , final time T , initial state \mathbf{z}_0
 - 2: **Input:** Model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (r, K, b, m, c, a, n, A, s, p_{decay}, q)$
 - 3: **Input:** Parameter bounds $(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max})$
 - 4: Generate N parameter sets using Latin Hypercube Sampling
 - 5: **for** $i = 1$ to N **do**
 - 6: Select parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}_i$
 - 7: Numerically integrate the model on $[0, T]$
 - 8: Store terminal state values $(Z_1(T), Z_2(T))$
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: Apply rank transformation to all sampled parameters
 - 11: Apply rank transformation to output variables $Z_1(T)$ and $Z_2(T)$
 - 12: **for** each parameter θ_j **do**
 - 13: Remove linear effects of remaining parameters via regression
 - 14: Compute residuals of θ_j and corresponding output
 - 15: Compute PRCC as Pearson correlation between residuals
 - 16: Compute corresponding p -value
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: Construct PRCC and p -value tables for $Z_1(T)$ and $Z_2(T)$
 - 19: Generate bar plots of PRCC values for each output variable
 - 20: Annotate bar plots with significance markers based on p -values
 - 21: Generate residual scatter plots for each parameter
 - 22: Overlay least-squares regression lines on scatter plots
 - 23: Annotate scatter plots with PRCC values and significance indicators
 - 24: **Output:** Numerical PRCC measures and graphical summaries highlighting parameter influence and statistical significance
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Pseudocode 5 Computation of PRCC with residual analysis and significance assessment

- 1: **Input:** Ranked parameter matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times p}$
- 2: **Input:** Ranked model output vector $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^N$
- 3: **Input:** Parameter names $\{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_p\}$
- 4: Initialize PRCC vector $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and p -value vector $\mathbf{pval} \in \mathbb{R}^p$
- 5: **for** $j = 1$ to p **do**
- 6: Extract ranked parameter vector \mathbf{X}_j
- 7: Form matrix \mathbf{X}_{-j} by excluding \mathbf{X}_j
- 8: Regress \mathbf{X}_j on $[\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{X}_{-j}]$ and compute residuals

$$\mathbf{R}_{X_j} = \mathbf{X}_j - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_j$$

- 9: Regress \mathbf{Y} on $[\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{X}_{-j}]$ and compute residuals

$$\mathbf{R}_Y = \mathbf{Y} - \widehat{\mathbf{Y}}$$

- 10: Compute PRCC as Pearson correlation

$$R_j = \text{corr}(\mathbf{R}_{X_j}, \mathbf{R}_Y)$$

- 11: Compute corresponding p -value for R_j
 - 12: Generate residual scatter plot $(\mathbf{R}_{X_j}, \mathbf{R}_Y)$
 - 13: Overlay least-squares regression line
 - 14: Annotate plot with PRCC value and significance marker
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **Output:** PRCC vector \mathbf{R} and significance vector \mathbf{pval}
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NOTE: In figure 9 within the manuscript, instead of using bar plots, we have plotted the prcc values for each parameter for a large number of time points (equally spaced from 0 to 200 with step size 1) making it look like a bunch of continuous curves.